

Short Communication

Centralized Medical Registration Services (One-Point Registration): Need of the Hour

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ABSTRACT

A Medical Practitioner after obtaining the required qualifications gets registered with the respective State Medical Council or the National Medical Council. If the person is registered with a State Medical Council and shifts his practice to another state, he has to re-register with the other state after obtaining No-Objection-Certificate from his previously registered Medical Council. When a Medical Practitioner applies for a job or vacancy position, along with filling the application form, one also has to submit all required documents, right from school certificates to post-graduation degrees. This application process becomes cumbersome particularly when one has to apply for multiple positions and that too in a short period of time. A Centralized Medical Registration System which is updated timely by the candidate and verified by the Registration Agency can serve as a great tool for both the recruiters and the candidates. There are international services like ECFMG, ERAS and EPIC which provide a registration and verification process for the candidate in exchange for a fee. The candidate while applying for a position has to just share his registration ID with the portal and the recruiter can access the profile of the candidate. It becomes the responsibility of the applicant to keep the profile updated with timely addition of newly acquired qualifications, certifications and work-experiences.

Keywords: Medical Documents, Medical Certificates, Centralized Services, Medical Application, Unified Registration.

INTRODUCTION

A Registered Medical Practitioner (RMP) is one whose name is registered on the Indian Medical Register. A Medical Practitioner after obtaining the required qualifications gets registered with the respective State Medical Council or the National Medical Council. For whatever reason, a RMP who is registered with one State Medical Council shifts his practice to another state, he has to re-register with the other state, after obtaining No-

Objection-Certificate from his previously registered Medical Council.¹

When a Medical Practitioner applies for a job or vacancy position, along with filling the application form, one also has to submit all required documents, right from school certificates to specialty/super-specialty certificates. A RMP who has done MBBS/MD and already registered on the Indian Medical Register, again has to submit all documents from School Certificate to Postgraduate Degree.² The same has to be done for every job application. This application

process becomes cumbersome particularly when one has to apply for multiple positions and that too in a short period of time.

Super-specialists which are a rare breed of medical professionals at the moment can be practicing in multiple cities/metros in year. If they are registered with a particular State Medical Council then it becomes difficult for them to show their license in different states. However, a registration with the MCI/NMC gives them a license to practice pan-INDIA. In this regard, NMC has mandated that if an RMP is already with another state, then they cannot register with the NMC. Only fresh/first-time registrations are accepted in the National Medical Council.³ A faculty of any discipline during his career of 30-40 years can be placed in multiple positions and can have multiple work experiences. Filling-up of all the work experiences is required in the NMC Declaration Form and also while applying for positions in a new institute/organization.⁴ The candidate also has to attach the proofs of his work experience - relieving letter from previous institute and appointment order & joining report at next institute. This is also tedious process particularly when one has many job-shifts during one's career. This process also has to be done for every upcoming inspection. A faculty is required to fill the list of all the publications to his credit in the NMC Declaration Form and also while applying for job positions. A faculty can have 'n' number of publications ranging from 5 to 50 or even more. And this filling up of the publications also has to be done for every job application and every NMC inspection. Attaching the proofs of these publications is also required each and every time.

With the availability of online applications for various posts of Faculty, the process has no doubt become easier. But again, with each application one has to fill in all the work-experiences and all the publications every time. Also in online applications, the photo/signature/document requirements are such that one needs to have more than basic IT skills in submitting a properly filled application.² The photo & signature requirements in Pixels and KBs need good editing skills on a software or online platform (Table-1). The limiting file size of documents to be uploaded is also sometimes too harsh to get it right. All the above-mentioned issues faced in different spheres of medical practice can be corrected with a one-point registration and verification system. A Centralized Medical Registration System which is updated timely by the candidate and verified by the Registration Agency can serve as a great tool for both the recruiters and the candidates. There are international services like ECFMG (Educational Commission for Foreign Medical Graduates), ERAS (Electronic Residency Application Services) and EPIC (Electronic Portfolio of International Credentials) which provide a registration and verification process for the candidate in exchange for a fee.

These and other systems like these are followed in the developed countries like USA, UK, Canada, Australia etc. which requires a one-time registration and periodical updating, as and when required. The candidate while applying for a position has to just share his registration ID with the portal and the recruiter can access the profile of the candidate & other credentials & documents. It becomes the responsibility of the applicant to keep the profile updated with timely addition of newly acquired qualifications, certifications and work-experiences. And the Registration Entity has to verify the credentials of the candidate so that there are no fraudulent entries.

This Goal can be achieved by:

1. A Government body
2. A Private body
3. On PPP Model
4. Up gradation of the Existing System.

In Conclusion, a One-Point Registration Portal can have the following advantages:

- No need of Re-registering with different Medical Councils if a practitioner changes base from one state to another.
- No need of submitting all documents & publications while applying for different jobs. Just sharing the registered ID with the portal will suffice.
- A one-point registration & verification with the portal and periodical updating as and when required.
- No need to repeatedly present all the experience certificates of the previous job positions particularly when a candidate has multiple job changes during his/her career. Just once uploading the document & getting its verification done on the portal will be adequate.

Table-I: Guidelines for scanning the Photograph and Signature²

Photograph	Signature
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The photograph must be a recent passport size color picture. - The picture should be in color, against a light-colored, preferably white, background. - Caps, hats and dark glasses are not acceptable. - Religious headwear is allowed but it must not cover your face. - Dimensions 200 x 230 pixels (preferred) - Size of file should be between 20 KB - 50 KB - Ensure that the size of the scanned image is not more than 50 KB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The applicant has to sign on white paper with Black ink pen - The signature will be used to be put on the Hall Ticket and wherever necessary - If the Applicant's signature on the answer script, at the time of the examination, does not match the signature on the Hall Ticket, the applicant will be disqualified. - Dimensions 140 x 60 pixels (preferred) - Size of the file should be between 10 KB - 20 KB - Ensure that the size of the scanned image is not more than 20 KB

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